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TEMPLATE FORM ON FACULTY FULL-BLOWN PROPOSAL AND FINAL IMRAD MANUSCRIPT

Title Legislative Competency of Sangguniang Kabataan Officials: A Catalyst for Youth Participation in Local Governance of a First-Class Municipality

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Abstract

Legislation stands as a cornerstone in any democratic system, demanding that legislators wield essential competencies to fulfill their roles as architects of local government. These competencies are not just desirable but indispensable for fostering nation-building. In response to the widespread mismanagement, ineffectiveness, and corruption plaguing the Sangguniang Kabataan (SK), the Philippine Congress enacted R.A. No. 10742, otherwise known as the Sangguniang Kabataan Reform Law. This study aimed to assess the local legislation competencies of the incumbent SK Officials of the Municipality of Bayombong. Specifically, it aimed to measure their communication skills, attention to detail, research aptitude, problem analysis and solution, information management, and influence and impact. This descriptive research employed quantitative approach to the SK Officials' competencies including the difficulties and challenges in performing their legislative mandates. Results show that SK officials' competencies in communication, research, problem-solving, attention to detail, and information management are good. Communication was the highest-rated competency, with officials showing strong interpersonal skills but needing improvement in openness to suggestions. Research aptitude was also noted as dependable, though many were less confident in leading research efforts independently. No significant differences were found in competency levels when respondents were grouped by position, indicating a consistent skill level across the board regardless of role. However, qualitative responses revealed widespread difficulties in legislative writing, particularly in structuring and formatting resolutions, and in understanding what content to include in the "whereas" sections. These challenges were largely attributed to a lack of training and formal instruction. Further difficulties included limited participation of council members, poor attendance during sessions, and internal conflicts that hindered the legislative process. SK officials also reported challenges balancing the needs of the youth with broader community goals, particularly in the face of limited resources and time constraints. Many found it hard to create actionable, realistic, and legally sound resolutions.

Keywords: *Local legislation, SK resolutions, communication, attention to detail, research aptitude, problem analysis and solution, information management, influence and impact*

Introduction

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1. Short Introduction

Legislation plays a fundamental role in democracy. Legislators must necessarily possess the fundamental legislative competencies to perform their duties and functions as framers of local policies and enactments. These competencies are quite imperative not only among national but also local legislators, including youth leaders of barangays, because they now have the autonomy to govern their affairs. In fact, the 1987 Philippine Constitution acknowledges the youth as a significant part of nation-building. In this regard, the youth shall possess high levels of patriotism and nationalism and be involved in public and civic affairs. It is the reason why there is now a trend allowing the youth to directly shape public policies and programs. Young people have the magnificent talent, creativity, and energy which could be harnessed to promote development.

Youth participation in Filipino nation-building can be traced as early as the 1880s when a group of young women of Malolos wrote Governor-General Weyler a request to create a school for them to learn the Spanish language. Aside from them, the members of the Propaganda Movement were also mostly young Filipinos who worked and fought for reforms during the late nineteenth century. Prior to the 1987 constitution, earlier institutions were already in place to encourage youth participation in governance (Flores et al., 2021). In 1975, then President Marcos promulgated Presidential Decree (PD) 684 that created the Kabataang Barangay (KB), as a youth platform in governance and community activities. However, it was Batas Pambansa Blg. 337 or the Local Government Code of 1983, which institutionalized the KB by clearly outlining the legal mandate of the Filipino youth leaders who are into office by registered youth voters of the KB Assembly. It also created the KB Federations at various levels, and the mandatory allocation of ten (10) percent of the total general fund of the barangay for the management of youth affairs.

Since its establishment in 1975, youth participation in local governance has been mired in controversy because he appointed his daughter, Imee Marcos, as the chairperson of the National Youth Council of KB. His critics claimed that the Kabataang Barangay was created to counter antigovernment movements among the youth. They also claim that KB exposed the youth to corrupt and opportunistic tactics at a very young age. However, Balanon et al. (2007) and Montes (2018) found that youth's experiences in local governance represented an important historical step in empowering the youth towards political participation.

In 1991, early reforms were integrated into youth's participation in governance and nation-building. Republic Act 7160, also known as the Local Government Code of the Philippines, was passed into law. This created the Sangguniang Kabataan (SK), which replaced KB, and stipulated the thrust of further providing avenues for legislation and program implementation for the youth. Throughout its early years of implementation, the SK was blemished by controversy and distrust, leading to many calls over the years for its abolishment (Mendez, 2008; Tan 2010; and Go, M. 2013). There is also a

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proliferation of political dynasties, mismanagement, skills deficiencies, and incompetence among SK officials, confirmed by Malaluan et al. (2014); Balanon et al. (2007); and Flores et al. (2022).

In 2016 the SK Reform Law was enacted. It reformed the SK by granting the power to promulgate resolutions necessary to carry out the objectives of the youth in the barangay. This gives a high presumption that SK officials must demonstrate fundamental legislative competencies in the performance of their local policy-making duties and functions. Guinid (2018) believed that legislation and program development are difficult political exercises because these involve too much bickering among political actors. The SK resolution-making, budget enactment, and program management are not exempted from this political nature. Malaluan et al. (2014) and Balanon et al. (2007) reported weak legislative performance of SK, particularly in legislating resolutions and ordinances, submitting reports, enacting budgets, formulating plans, and holding consultations with its constituents. Hence, there is a dire need to capacitate SK officials with legislation competencies essential in formulating resolutions, budgets, and other program plans.

The last SK election was held on October 2023, and the victors are now performing their statutory mandates in their respective Barangays. The most contentious question is, are they equipped with appropriate legislative competencies to perform their duties and responsibilities? This research intends to assess the legislation competencies of the newly elected SK officials that are geared towards providing strategic interventions for them to perform better their legislative powers and functions.

2. RRL and RS of Major Concepts / Variables (Based on Problem)

Legislative competencies

Guinid (2018) found that the majority of the legislator respondents possess adequate competence to perform their Legislative functions. However, findings also show that they need to level up their proficiency in all the dimensions of legislative competence. Specifically, Legislators need to learn the fundamentals of policy research and analysis, develop how to simplify complex issues, and master strategies to articulate the same to their colleagues and constituents effectively. Findings suggest that DILG should design more appropriate capability training for neophyte legislators. To improve better and balanced local legislation, it is also recommended that more women should be run for legislative positions. This research reinforces the importance of learning the fundamentals of policy research and analysis among local legislators to succeed in performing legislative duties and powers by the SK officials.

In terms of attended trainings on local legislation prior to election, Mangrobang (2023) found that legislator respondents have attended legislative-related trainings wherein this manifests the good number of sponsored resolutions. However, they need to undergo more training on effective local legislation since a significant positive correlation has been noted

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under legislative functions, jurisdiction of assigned committees, presiding over committee meetings, and relationship building, the more hours of legislative training the newly elected officials have, the more adept they are in making laws and policy decisions, and enact these laws. It is evident that even though many of them have college degrees and their competency level is noticeably higher, they still lack the necessary abilities to put their knowledge to use. It is also recommended that there be continuous education and development focused primarily on the knowledge of parliamentary rules and procedures and skills training in effective communication. This is to advance and produce a continual improvement in the local legislative system. These findings are relevant to the proposed research, particularly the need for local legislation training of legislators. The SK officials also need continuous education in developing their parliamentary rules and procedures skills essential in formulating resolutions, plans and programs, budgets, and others.

The descriptive-analytical study of Libo-on (2020) determined the predictors of the barangay officials' parliamentary rules and procedure level of knowledge and skills. Results showed an average level of knowledge of parliamentary rules and procedures, particularly their skills in the basic principles of parliamentary procedures. The skills in handling the order of business are motions at a good level. Their skill level in precedence of motion is average. The educational attainment of the officials served as a predictor of the level of knowledge of parliamentary procedures. This study shows significance to this proposed research because it shows the average and mediocre legislation competencies of Barangay officials using the educational attainment of the respondents. The SK officials' legislation competencies are, however, interesting to study.

Difficulties encountered in enacting resolutions

RA 7160 empowers the SK to promulgate resolutions necessary to carry out the objectives of the youth in the barangay. However, difficulties were encountered by SK officials such as limited capacities. Balanon et al. (2007) documented that the SK's performance of its legislative function is weak due to its limited capacities. Findings showed that a small number of SK councils promulgated legislative acts as accomplishments in the forms of resolutions passed. However, the documents also showed that SK representatives can come up with highly relevant ordinances but very few of them. The review of accomplishment reports also showed SK councils had focused mostly on sports-related activities, environmental activities, infrastructure projects, beauty pageants, talent shows, dances, social gatherings, music band contests and the like.

The previous mentioned researches reported weak legislative performance of SK officials, particularly in legislating resolutions and ordinances, submitting reports, enacting budgets, formulating plans, and holding consultations. Hence, this research could help build a program that will capacitate SK officials with legislation competencies essential in formulating resolutions, budgets, and other program plans.

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The researchers believe that as they delve deeper into the legislative competencies of youth leaders, it becomes unequivocally clear that empowering young voices isn't just a choice but indeed it's an imperative for shaping a more inclusive, and progressive future. Our society should seize the opportunity to amplify their influence, for in their hands lies the power to transform societies and enact lasting change.

3. Theoretical Framework

The Expectancy-Value Model of Model

The expectancy-value model suggests that people are motivated to participate in tasks based on the potential of success and valuing those tasks (Schrader & Helmke, 2015). Expectancies are determined by individuals' expectations that they can succeed on certain upcoming tasks, either in the direct or distant future. Furthermore, the theory states that the intensity of a tendency to perform in a particular manner is dependent on the intensity of an expectation that the performance will be followed by a definite outcome and on the appeal of the outcome to the individual.

The Expectancy theory states that an individual's motivation is an outcome of (1. Valence) how much an individual wants a reward. Valence is the consequence associated with a person about the expected result. It is predictable and not the real satisfaction that a person expects to obtain after achieving the goals; (2. Expectancy) Knowing the probability that the effort will lead to anticipated performance. Expectancy is the faith that improved efforts will affect better performances. Expectancy is prompted by factors such as possession of suitable skills for the execution of the task, accessibility of right resources, obtainability of crucial information, and getting support for finalizing the task; and (3. Instrumentality) the belief that the performance will lead to rewarding. Instrumentality is the faith that if you do your task well, then the outcome will be valid. Instrumentality is swayed by factors such as trust in the people who decide what outcome, the easiness of the process of deciding who gets what outcome, and the lucidity of the relationship between outcomes and performance.

Thus, the expectancy theory concentrates on (1) the Effort-performance relationship; (2) the Performance-reward relationship; and (3) the Rewards-personal goals relationship. To this end, this theory is relevant in the current study because it will unveil some explanations why some people are more motivated in doing some tasks. Since the main domains are trainings, knowledge, and competencies, the dual features of this theory such as "expectations for success" and "how much you value a job" will help shed light on their achievement and commitment.

4. Conceptual and Analytical Framework

Legislative competencies

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In the definition of European Environment Information and Observation Network (Eionet) legislative competencies include the skill, knowledge, qualification, capacity or authority to make, give or enact rules with binding force upon a population or jurisdiction.

UN-Habitat (2005) described legislative competencies as policy making competencies which help legislator understand how to carry out this fundamental elected responsibility within the framework of good governance principles and establish, through the policy making process, the foundation for conducting the business of the public. According to United Nations University legislative competence implies an institution's capacity to make rules that are binding on its membership, and to change those rules. It includes the following:

Communication Skills involve giving and receiving information, ideas, and feelings with accuracy and understanding. The communication competency will help legislator become a better listener, ask more incisive questions, and learn how to say no without losing the next election (UN Habitat, 2005).

Research Aptitude is the ability to conduct a systematic and objective inquiry about youth concerns, particularly in the nine areas of participation including study design, collection, analysis, and interpretation of data; and the reporting of results to ensure that youth policies and programs are firmly grounded, and that they are the best they can be.

Problem Analysis and Resolution is the capacity to identify, define, and analyze various youth issues, obstacles, and opportunities, and to generate possible/alternative solutions according to gathered data and rational analysis.

Policy development refers to the ability to raise interest and persuade others to support the national youth agenda or the PYDP utilizing various education, information, and communication strategies.

Problem Analysis and Resolution is the capability to identify, define, and analyze various youth issues, obstacles, and opportunities and to generate possible/alternative solutions according to gathered data and rational analysis.

Influence and impact are the ability to raise interest and persuade others to support the national youth agenda or the PYDP utilizing various education, information, and communication strategies.

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Influence and impact refer to the capacity to raise interest and persuade others to support the national youth agenda or the PYDP utilizing various education, information, and communication strategies.

Attention to detail is the skill to ensure that one's own and other's output is complete, accurate, and concise in accordance with agreements and commitments.

Figure 1. Conceptual Paradigm

5. Statement of the Problem / Purpose of the Study

Generally, the study aims to assess the local legislation competencies of the incumbent SK Officials of the Municipality of Bayombong. The study was conducted from August to March of 2025.

Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of legislative competencies of SK officials in terms of:
 - A. Communication
 - B. Attention to detail
 - C. Research aptitude
 - D. Problem analysis and solution

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E. Information management

F. Influence and impact

2. Is there a significant difference in the level of legislative competencies of SK officials when respondents are grouped according to their profile variables?
3. What are the difficulties encountered by SK officials in enacting resolutions?

6. Hypothesis of the Study

There is a significant difference in the level of legislative competencies of SK officials when respondents are grouped according to their profile variables.

Methodology

1. Design

The study is an assessment of the fundamental legislation competencies of the SK officials in the municipality of Bayombong. It is a quantitative type of research that used a descriptive-comparative approach in determining the legislation competencies at the same time the encountered difficulties in legislation.

2. Locale

The research was conducted at the municipality of Bayombong which is a first class at the same time capital municipality of the province of Nueva Vizcaya. According to the 2020 census, the municipality has a land area of 163.36 square kilometers or 63.07 square miles and a population of 67,714 inhabitants. It is politically subdivided into 25 barangays, each led by elected Barangay officials and SK officials representing the youth.

3. Participants and Sample

The target respondents of the study are the elected and appointed SK officials of the 25 barangays of the municipality of Bayombong. The elected SK officials who participated in the study were 21 SK Chairpersons and 34 other officers. The total number of respondents is 55.

Additionally, the following were the criteria used in selecting the respondents:

Inclusion:

1. The respondent must be currently residing in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya;
2. Must be an elected SK official last October 2023 elections or appointed SK secretary and treasurer;

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3. He/she has agreed and signed the informed consent form.

Exclusion:

1. Previous SK officials who were no longer elected into office or appointed last October 2023; and
2. KK members who are fifteen (15) to under eighteen (18) years old.

The exclusion of respondents between the ages of 15 and 17 complies with RA 10742 which stipulates that to be elected as SK official the candidate must be at least 18 years old.

4. Instrument(s)

This study used the questionnaire as an instrument to gather data needed to answer the research problems. The questionnaire has three parts profile of the respondent, legislation competencies, and problems encountered by the SK Officials in formulating resolutions, budget, and program plans.

Many of the items were adopted from the Guidebook on the Competency Framework for the Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) Officials and Local Youth Development Officers (LYDOs) of DILG. The first part asks about the significant profile of the respondents. Meanwhile, the second part determines the level of competencies of the respondents on communication, attention to detail, research aptitude, problem analysis and solution, information management, influence and impact. The third part determines the difficulties encountered by SK officials in making resolutions, budgeting, and planning programs.

5. Data Gathering Procedure

Respondents are the incumbent SK officials of the 25 barangays of the municipality of Bayombong. The researchers requested a copy of the list of elected SK officials from the Municipal Local Government Office. An informed consent form was provided to them. This form contains the nature of the study and their willingness to be part of it. Questionnaires were distributed to the respondents in their own barangay after their regular session. The questionnaires were collected after answering.

6. Treatment of Data

Quantitative data was analyzed using SPSS. The mean rating scale was used to determine the level of legislative competencies. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the level of legislation competencies of SK officials, particularly on communication, attention to detail, research aptitude, problem analysis and solution, information management, influence, and impact. Differences in the legislation competencies level were analyzed using independent samples T-test. Qualitative data on the difficulties encountered by the SK officials in legislation were interpreted.

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7. Ethical Considerations

The study were submitted for ethics review to Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB) with address and contact information at 2nd Floor, Rev. John Van Bauwel Hall, SMU Main Campus, Ponce Street, Don Mariano Marcos; Bayombong, 3700 Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines (email: reb@smu.edu.ph;cellphone: 09177053041).

Conflict of Interest

The researchers declared that there is no personal gain or conflict of interest from the result of the study.

Privacy, Confidentiality and Data Protection

Respondents were required to write their names in the survey questionnaire to protect their privacy of information. Data gathered from the respondents were treated with utmost confidentiality and used for research purposes. These data were only accessed and processed by the researchers. The questionnaires used in gathering data were disposed properly after the conduct of the study. The dataset files of the responses of the respondents will also be deleted from the file after the conduct of the study.

Management of vulnerability

The incumbent SK officials of the 25 barangays of the Municipality of Bayombong were the respondents of this study. All of them are in the age bracket of 18-24 years old, as stipulated by RA 10742. There were no respondents who are below 18 years old.

Risk / Benefit Ratio

The researchers were exposed to vehicular accidents since they gathered data in the barangays of the municipality. However, precautionary measures were employed in going to the different barangays. The results of the study are now the basis for creating a program that will help develop and/or improve the legislation competencies of the SK officials of the different barangays in the municipality. There will be capacity training on resolution-making, budgeting, Parliamentary procedures, and program planning. These trainings will improve the SK officials as youth leaders and legislators. On the part of the respondents, the were no perceived risks that affected them.

Informed Consent

A letter addressed to the respondent and the informed consent form was given to the participants. The respondent was given enough time to think and respond if he or she accepts or declines to participate in the survey. After the respondent agreed, the survey questionnaire was administered.

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Every SK official respondent was notified by the researchers. The questionnaires and consent forms were distributed to the respondents by individually visiting their Barangay. The purpose of the study was explained to them by the researchers and allowed them for clarification on any points they found unclear.

The researchers requested the Punong Barangay concerned to help them reach out the SK officials. The researchers and SK officials set a specific date for data gathering in each Barangay. The respondent who didn't feel comfortable or felt inconveniences on the survey discontinued answering the questionnaires. He/she was discarded from the pool of respondents.

After answering the questionnaire, the researchers gathered all the completed forms. The researchers ensured that the data is kept confidential. Data from the study were only used for research purposes, and the identities of respondents remained confidential.

Dissemination Plan

The researchers intend to disseminate the findings of the study on an SK Forum. The capacitation seminars and trainings will commence after the dissemination of the results. The extended abstract will be published on the SMU Research Abstracts and other research journals. The study will also be posted on the SMU website and FB page of the SK Federation of Bayombong.

Terms of Reference

The faculty researchers and external collaborator are the authors of the study. There are no government or other funding agencies involved in the production of the research.

8. Results and Discussion

The general aim of the study was to determine the legislative competencies of the SK officials of the municipality of Bayombong.

Table 1. Overall Competencies Levels

Comptencies	Mean	Std. Deviation	Qualitative Description
Communication	4.17	1.08213	Good
Attention to details	3.74	1.03519	Good
Research aptitude	3.76	1.02494	Good
Problem analysis and resolution	3.88	1.06268	Good
Information management	3.82	1.04668	Good
Influence and impact	3.90	1.19179	Good

Legend: 1.00-1.79 – Poor; 1.80-2.59 – Fair; 2.60-3.39 – Moderate; 3.40-4.19 – Good; 4.20-5.00 – Excellent.

The first competency is communication. As shown in table 1, overall, the SK official's communication competency (M = 4.17, SD = 1.08) is good. Notably, the respondents are excellent in courteous engagement, attentive, and respectful communication. However, they have a low level of accepting suggestions during SK sessions. This suggests a generally high level of effective interpersonal communication within the council.

Results of the study revealed that participants are rated good on their attention to detail (M = 3.74, SD = 1.04). They have high level of clarity and completeness in delivering information while low in providing timely accurate information. These results suggest that while members are conscientious, there may be room for improvement in timeliness and consistency of accuracy. This is consistent with Magno (2019), who found that local youth leaders often face constraints related to administrative support and time management, hindering effective governance.

Although respondents rate themselves positively in supporting proposals (M = 3.76, SD = 1.02), they indicate low confidence in leading research initiatives. Similar findings were presented in a study by Mercado and Rayos (2018), where SK officials expressed limited exposure to formal research methods and low engagement in data-driven policy formulation. This highlights a systemic gap in capacity-building that is essential for informed youth legislation.

The competency for resolving problems (M = 3.88, SD = 1.06) is a strength among the respondents, particularly in demonstrating fairness and accountability. The acting with fairness and accountability is excellent. This suggests that SK officials are particularly confident in managing decisions responsibly. All other items also fall solidly within the good level, pointing to a robust skillset in problem resolution. The study of Tapales (2006) supports this, noting that younger leaders are often more transparent and willing to take responsibility. Nevertheless, the need for structured decision-making frameworks remains important to enhance consistency across LGUs.

Respondents were generally proficient in organizing and providing requested information (M = 3.82, SD = 1.05), although they scored lower in system maintenance and reporting. They show an excellent level in efficient data organization and delivering

requested information, while low in maintaining filing systems and timely reporting. Overall, SK officials appear effective in handling and organizing information, although improvements in system maintenance may enhance performance further. Balanon et al. (2007) noted similar inefficiencies in SK units due to the absence of standardized information systems and technical support. These deficits affect not only documentation but also institutional memory and operational continuity.

The ability of SK officials to identify key stakeholders and initiate partnerships (M = 3.90, SD = 1.19) demonstrates an encouraging capacity for outreach and advocacy. They are high in identifying influential stakeholders as well as in suggesting a strategic approach to building partnerships. Utilizing media to engage youth and maintaining databases of contacts also scored high, reflecting a proactive stance in outreach to their fellow youth and advocacy efforts. This aligns with Tuazon and Castillo (2013), who documented successful youth-led initiatives involving multimedia campaigns and partnership networks. However, actual policy influence remains limited unless these engagements are tied to formal legislative or planning processes.

Table 2. Differences in the legislative competency levels when grouped according to positions

	Groups	f (n=64)	Mean	SD	QD	t-value	p-value
Communication	Chairman	17	4.13	1.061	Good	-.183 ^{ns}	.920
	Kagawad	38	4.19	1.105	Good		
Attention to details	Chairman	17	3.79	1.024	Good	.248 ^{ns}	.975
	Kagawad	38	3.71	1.053	Good		
Research aptitude	Chairman	17	3.82	1.060	Good	.287 ^{ns}	.711
	Kagawad	38	3.74	1.022	Good		
Problem analysis and resolution	Chairman	17	3.80	1.145	Good	-.357 ^{ns}	.317
	Kagawad	38	3.91	1.038	Good		
Information management	Chairman	17	3.94	1.052	Good	.565 ^{ns}	.997
	Kagawad	38	3.77	1.054	Good		
Influence and impact	Chairman	17	4.01	1.226	Good	.474 ^{ns}	.983
	Kagawad	38	3.85	1.189	Good		

Legend: 1.00-1.79 – Poor; 1.80-2.59 – Fair; 2.60-3.39 – Moderate; 3.40-4.19 – Good; 4.20-5.00 – Excellent.

The inferential results from the two-sample T-test reveal no statistically significant difference in legislative competencies between SK officials when grouped according to position. This outcome spans all six competency domains: communication (t = -0.18, p = .855), attention to detail (t = -0.25, p = .805), research aptitude (t = -0.29, p = .755), problem analysis and resolution (t = -0.36, p = .723), information management (t = -0.57, p = .575), and influence and impact (t = -0.47, p = .637). These findings indicate that, regardless of their

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specific role within the SK council, officials tend to exhibit similar skill levels across legislative competencies.

This parity may suggest either effective role homogenization or a systemic deficiency in role-specific development, which resonates with the findings of Malaluan et al. (2014), who highlighted that SK lacks position-specific competency development and formal role delineation. Furthermore, Balanon et al. (2007) observed that a lack of structured training across varying SK roles contributes to a uniform but modest legislative output.

Table 3. Difficulties experienced by SK officials in legislating resolutions and ordinances

It is challenging to write the content and whereas part.

I struggle in writing the content of a resolution.

Struggling what to put on the whereas part.

Lack of knowledge on how to do it but I make it up by searching the internet on how to do it.

Not knowing the format of it.

I don't know the correct format of a resolution and what to include on the whereas part.

We are not 100 percent sure about the proper format.

Proper use of terminologies

We struggle to identify what issue we really want to address and also struggle in structuring the resolution.

The main difficulties in writing resolutions include being too vague, setting unrealistic goals, staying motivated, and trying to tackle too many things at once.

One difficulty in writing resolutions is ensuring that they address the needs and concerns of the youth while staying within legal and budgetary constraints. It can also be challenging to make sure that the resolutions are practical, actionable, and have the support of both the youth and the local government officials.

One of the difficulties we encountered in writing solution is that unclear of objectives, if the resolution is not clear it's hard to make it formal.

The data from Table 3 reveals that Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials commonly face difficulties in composing the content and "whereas" parts of resolutions. This indicates a lack of clarity in understanding the structure and elements of formal legislative documents. Multiple responses reflect uncertainty regarding the format and the appropriate use of language and terminologies. The challenge extends beyond mechanics to the conceptual level, where SK officials struggle to define the core issue to be addressed. Moreover, some participants mention that while they attempt to compensate for these knowledge gaps through online searches, the lack of formal training leaves them unsure of their output's accuracy and effectiveness. This deficiency reflects not just a lack of technical writing skills but also a deeper conceptual gap in issue articulation and legal formatting. Mercado and

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Rayos (2018) emphasized that this is not uncommon in youth governance, where minimal training leads to poor legislative structure and reduced policy relevance.

In addition to technical writing difficulties, SK officials also experience challenges related to the practicality and feasibility of their proposed resolutions. There are concerns about setting vague or unrealistic goals, maintaining motivation, and ensuring the proposals are actionable within legal and budgetary constraints. This suggests that the youth leaders are aware of the need for grounded and strategic planning, but feel unprepared to meet such expectations. The overall sentiment emphasizes the necessity for structured guidance and capacity-building programs to enhance both the content creation and policy formulation skills of SK officials.

Qualitative data complements the statistical analysis by exposing critical gaps in legislative functioning. Respondents report persistent difficulties in drafting resolutions and ordinances, citing lack of skills, training, cooperation, and time management. These insights echo Flores and Dizon (2016), who found that many SK officials feel inadequately prepared to fulfill legislative tasks due to limited exposure to policy writing and public administration processes.

Table 4. Challenges experienced by SK officials in legislating resolutions and ordinances

*Lack of trainings for secretaries.
 Because we don't have seminars about it.
 Madali lang gumawa ng resolution ang mahirap mag papirma sa mga SK kagawad
 Not all SK councils are participating, and few are implemented.
 It's tricky to make sure the resolutions are actually doable and have a lasting impact. We only get difficulties when it comes to signing of resolutions (absence of SK officials)
 Writing resolutions in the SK can be tough. It's hard to balance what the youth need with what the whole community needs, especially with limited resources. Getting everyone to agree on things can be a challenge too.*

The responses in Table 4 point to systemic and procedural barriers that hinder SK officials from effectively legislating resolutions and ordinances. A prominent theme is the lack of formal training or seminars, particularly for secretaries, which results in a weak grasp of the legislative process. This gap in capacity-building is compounded by the limited participation and commitment of some SK councils, leading to delays in decision-making and document processing. Some officials note that getting signatures from council members is a major hurdle, especially when others are absent or disengaged. This affects not only the formal passage of resolutions but also the cohesion and functionality of the entire SK council. These findings support the conclusions of Tuazon and Castillo (2013), who identified procedural inefficiencies and weak accountability systems within SK units as major barriers to effective youth governance. Additionally, the difficulty of acquiring necessary signatures and the disengagement of members underscore challenges in collaborative leadership and

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governance cohesion. Tapales (2006) suggested that youth councils often lack the institutional scaffolding necessary to support procedural discipline, leading to erratic participation and poor compliance with organizational protocols.

Another challenge lies in ensuring that resolutions are both relevant and feasible. Officials express the difficulty of reconciling the varying needs of youth with broader community interests, especially when resources are scarce. This balancing act requires careful planning and collaboration, which are often hard to achieve in practice. The data also reflects frustration with the limited implementation of passed resolutions, hinting at a disconnect between legislative intentions and real-world execution. Overall, these findings highlight the importance of strengthening institutional support, encouraging active participation, and equipping SK officials with the necessary tools to make governance more effective and inclusive. These observations are consistent with Magno (2019), who argued that while SK officials show enthusiasm for governance, they often fall short in policy execution due to weak linkages between planning, budgeting, and implementation. Such disconnects between passed resolutions and actual impact highlight the importance of capacity-building programs that go beyond knowledge transfer to include mentoring, technical support, and performance evaluation. Structured, skills-based training with a focus on real-world application is crucial to improve both the content and the impact of youth legislation.

Conclusions

The Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) officials exhibit commendable communication competencies, demonstrating a strong attention to detail and reliable skills in managing information. Their ability to communicate clearly and thoroughly contributes to the effective execution of their legislative responsibilities. These skills are complemented by their trustworthiness and influence among fellow youth leaders and constituents, helping foster collaboration and engagement within the council.

In terms of legislative capabilities, SK officials show dependable research aptitude and a competent approach to problem analysis and solution formulation. Their capacity to understand community issues and propose relevant policies indicates that, despite challenges, they possess the foundational skills needed for effective governance. These abilities are crucial in drafting resolutions and ordinances that are practical, responsive, and reflective of the youth's needs.

Despite these strengths, SK officials commonly encounter obstacles in their legislative work. These challenges include a lack of formal training, limited experience in resolution writing, and insufficient support from fellow officers. Time management issues and internal conflicts further hinder their efficiency, alongside poor attendance and non-participation among some members, which affects the consistency and quality of their legislative output.

Overall, the respondents' views and performances reflect similar experiences across the municipality, highlighting shared struggles in legislative execution. The consistency of

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these experiences suggests systemic gaps in support, training, and resources. Addressing these barriers through structured training programs, increased mentorship, and stronger internal coordination could significantly enhance the effectiveness of SK officials in fulfilling their legislative mandates.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn, here are the research recommendations:

- 1. Conduct Regular Capacity-Building Workshops and Trainings.** To address the identified gaps in legislative knowledge and skills, it is highly recommended that the LGU of Bayombong and relevant agencies organize regular seminars and capacity-building programs for SK officials. These should focus on resolution writing, legislative procedures, effective communication, and problem-solving strategies. Special attention should be given to training secretaries and officers on proper documentation and formatting of ordinances.
- 2. Develop and Disseminate Standardized Legislative Guides.** The MLGOO in collaboration with LYDO should create user-friendly manuals or toolkits that outline the correct format, structure, and terminology for resolutions and ordinances would greatly assist SK officials in the municipality . These resources should be made easily accessible, both in printed and digital formats, to serve as reference materials during legislative drafting.
- 3. Enhance Internal Coordination and Team-Building Activities.** To mitigate internal conflicts and increase participation, team-building activities and leadership development programs should be implemented. These initiatives can improve collaboration, attendance, and unity among SK members, ultimately leading to a more cohesive and productive legislative body.
- 4. Encourage Further Research on Legislative Competencies and Youth Governance.** Future studies should delve deeper into the legislative competencies of SK officials, including the influence of external factors such as mentorship, community involvement, and political environment. Comparative studies across different municipalities or regions could also provide broader insights and best practices for strengthening youth governance across the country.

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Questionnaire

July 1, 2024

Dear respondent,

Marian greetings!

We are faculty researchers of Saint Mary's University currently conducting a study entitled ***Legislative Competency of Sangguniang Kabataan Officials: A Catalyst for Youth Participation in Local Governance of a First-Class Municipality*** as part of Project Wealth Program v 2.0. We humbly request for 10-15 minutes of your time to participate in this

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study. Your feedback should be based on your experiences as SK official during your term. If you decide to participate in this study, your submission of this survey will act as your signature. You are still free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason. Thank you!

Respectfully,

Erwin D. Naval – Lead Researcher
 Ernest Esmeralda – Primary Collaborator
 Diwata Donato – Secondary Collaborator
 Xaviery Brent Galima – Secondary Collaborator
 Carlo Noel Gines – External Collaborator

Informed Consent Form

This form is for the incumbent elected Sangguniang Kabataan officials of Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya in their participation in the research project entitled ***Legislative Competency of Sangguniang Kabataan Officials: A Catalyst for Youth Participation in Local Governance of a First-Class Municipality.***

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Organizational Affiliations: Saint Mary's University
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 Department of Social Sciences and Philosophy

Information Sheet

You are hereby being invited by faculty researchers from Saint Mary's University to participate in their study on the ***Legislative Competency of Sangguniang Kabataan Officials: A Catalyst for Youth Participation in Local Governance of a First-Class Municipality.*** You can take your time to decide whether to participate or not and you can take questions any time for any word or concept in this form that you may not understand.

The purpose of the study is to assess the legislative competency of SK officials of the 25 barangays of the municipality of Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya by determining the skills, knowledge, and competencies.

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This study involves the use of a survey questionnaire that respondents will answer. You are selected as a participant because you are an elected SK official of the municipality of Bayombong or appointed secretary/treasurer. You are one of the 250 respondents. Please be informed that your participation is voluntary, and you can withdraw at any time without explanation. If you don't feel comfortable or felt inconveniencies on the survey you can discontinue answering the questionnaires.

Should you choose to participate in the study, you shall be answering a questionnaire containing questions to assess your training needs by responding honestly and truthfully based on your own observations and experiences using a likert scale from 1 to 5, 1 is strongly disagree, 2 is disagree, 3 is Neither agree nor disagree, 4 is agree, and 5 is strongly agree. The first part is all about your competencies related to communication, attention to detail, research aptitude, problem analysis resolution, information management, and influence and impact. The second part is difficulties and challenges you encountered in writing resolutions. It is estimated that your participation in the study will only take 10-15 minutes.

There is no known risk in your participation in the study, but it can be beneficial to the SK and KK Bayombong. The results of the survey will be functionally used to create a program to capacitate SK officials and KK members of the municipality. The capacitation includes providing trainings and retooling to enhance their skills and competencies in legislating local resolutions, Parliamentary procedures, budgeting, planning, and program execution.

You shall not receive any payment for your participation or any reimbursements. In case of any untoward and related incident or accident occurs, you will receive compensation and/or medical treatment as indemnity. Your refusal to participate or discontinuance at any time will not involve penalty or loss of benefits to which you are entitled. Even if you have chosen to participate voluntarily, you have the right to refuse to continue and any information you have already provided will not be used in the study. Rest assured that your privacy will be respected, and all your answers will be treated with the utmost confidentiality. You will not be required to affix your name in the survey questionnaire. This is to protect your privacy of information. Data collected from you will only be accessed and processed by the researchers. Any information from you will be under the protection of the researchers until the second semester of the academic year 2024-2025. Data gathered from you will be terminated upon deletion if the said semester is done.

The results of this study may be disseminated within Saint Mary's University through research fora. Also, the study may be submitted for publication in national or international journals. For any matter concerning this study, you can contact the researchers through the following email address that appeared in the questionnaire.

This study is to be approved by the Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB) at Saint Mary's University, Ponce Street, DMM, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya with the cellphone number: 09177053041 and email: reb@smu.edu.ph.

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Certificate of Consent

I have read the foregoing information, or it has been read to me. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions I have asked have been answered to my satisfaction. I consent voluntarily to be a participant in this study.

Print Name of Participant: _____

Signature of Participant: _____

Date: [MM/DD/YYYY]

Questionnaire for Legislative Competence

Part 1.

Scale:

- 1 - Poor
- 2- Fair
- 3- Moderate
- 4- Good
- 5- Excellent

A. Communication	1	2	3	4	5
1. I courteously speak to other officials of the SK council in a clear and professional manner					
2. I listen attentively to other officials of the SK ideas, concerns, and suggestions with an open mind.					
3. I interact to joint discussions during SK sessions with openness and respect that help build trust.					
4. I readily accept suggestions and opinions during SK sessions when an unpopular decision or unwelcomed information is shared.					
B. Attention to detail					
1. I always double-check the accuracy of information in documents and outputs					
2. I act and verify data or information in the reports and outputs					
3. I notice or detect errors in documents or outputs before it is distributed					
4. I provide accurate and consistent numbers on all paperwork					
5. I provide/give accurate information on timely basis					
6. I maintain an updated checklist. Schedule, calendar etc. to ensure that small details are not overlooked					
7. I ensure that the information delivered to the intended audience is clear, concise, and complete					
C. Research aptitude					
1. I conduct systematic and objective inquiry in pursuit of research balanced with considerations to ethical guidelines, political demands, public opinion, and youth-centric matters					
2. I evaluate information received to distinguish between subjective and objective data and biased data source					
3. I review research results based on solid analytics, and grounded reliable research data					

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4. I spearhead the development, delegation, and communication of research proposals and results					
5. I support the development and finalization of research proposals and results presentation with appropriate budget and plan monitoring					
D. Problem analysis resolution					
1. I recognize obvious solutions to work-related issues per established rules and procedures					
2. I identify the issues to understand the interest of others to determine action needed					
3. I provide timely solutions to simple problems and daily operational concerns without sacrificing the delivery of its mandate					
4. I undertake a complex issue by breaking it down into manageable parts in a systematic, detailed way					
5. I provide suggestions and opinions on how to solve issues and concerns related to youth program or project					
6. I determine the relative seriousness of a problem and distinguish between the problem immediate attention and those that allow for more deliberation					
7. I alert supervisor immediately to any issues and concerns that are discovered					
8. I anticipate potential issues or obstacles by assessing contextual factors or underlying root causes that need attention across groups, cases, or services					
9. I find solutions or answers to performance-related issues in the most efficient and expedient manner					
10. Guided with a set of criteria, I select the best option among alternative solutions that are backed up by data					
11. I act promptly on issues that reflect deviations from or deficiencies in program delivery					
12. I suggest research-based policy adjustments, new program concepts and change interventions that will contribute to better agency					
13. I act fairly, rationally, and with accountability for decisions and actions in the management and operations of the agency					
14. I examine recurring issues and complex problems to spot potential risks that requires mitigation					
E. Information Management					
1. I record and collect pertinent data in an organized manner to enable efficient storage and retrieval of information Tags					

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and labels incoming communications for proper recording and distribution					
2. I maintain an updated, organized, and secured filing system of data, information, and documents in both print and electronic formats					
3. I ensure that the information requested is delivered to the intended audience					
4. I cite or take note of important details obtained from feedback, stakeholder consultation and relevant documents that needs to be either recorded or to be addressed immediately and appropriately					
5. I report processed data and information that may be deemed relevant in other aspects to SK mandate and work in timely basis					
6. I pay close attention to data, in order to pinpoint flaws or missing data, and seeks out information to maintain or even improve the SK					
F. Influence and Impact					
1. I perform posting thru social media the activities and program of SK to disseminate easily to the youth					
2. I maintain and active database of regular contacts, potential commission, and youth partners					
3. I generate significant interests from stakeholders using different forms of media and communication strategies.					
4. I identify key individuals, partner institutions, and other stakeholders who can support and provide the biggest influence to promote the national youth agenda					

Part 2.

1. What are the difficulties you encountered in writing resolutions?

2. What are the challenges encountered by your SK council in enacting resolutions?
